

PERCEPTION OF SENIOR CITIZENS ON PAID VALUE-ADDED COMMUNITY PHARMACY SERVICES IN DASMARINAS, CAVITE

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ABSTRACT

Over these past few decades, the responsibility of the community pharmacist has evolved from its traditional roles of dispensing medications to improving patient-centered care and pharmacist-patient contact. Today, community pharmacists play a vital role in improving patients' health-related quality of life and obtaining good clinical results at a low cost by interacting directly with them through value-added pharmacy services. The research aims to explore the perceptions of the Filipino for such services, specifically senior citizen living in Dasmarinas Cavite for such services. Among the socio-demographic backgrounds, income level and educational attainment are among the factors that has a strong relationship with their attitude on paying. Furthermore, the awareness of senior citizens on value-added community pharmacy services are strongly correlated with their attitude on paying. That is to say that as their level of awareness increases, their attitude on paying also increases.

Keywords: *value-added pharmacy services, attitude on paying, senior citizen*

INTRODUCTION

A community pharmacist's day-to-day activities are defined by a wide variety of clinical and non-clinical tasks and skills, according to Joda & Oyenekan in 2013. Community pharmacists are well positioned to provide medication and health management services that complement general practitioner and allied health service offerings as accessible primary care health providers, according to a study conducted by Yong et al. in 2021.

Over the past decades, however, the responsibility of the community pharmacist has evolved from its traditional role to improving patient-centered care and pharmacist-patient contact. Pharmacists are critical in improving patients' health-related quality of life and obtaining good clinical results at a low cost by interacting directly with them (Iskandar et al., 2017). The need for a functioning healthcare system drastically changed, especially in South-East Asia, according to Hermansyah et al. in 2015. As stated by Desselle et al. in 2019, pharmacy has always been regarded as a “service” field continually evolving, developing services that add value to the medication use process, including public health services. A trend is developing for community pharmacists to serve as care extenders to address primary care physician shortages and the significant issues and costs associated with improper drug usage (Joda & Oyenekan, 2013). The evolution and diversification of these services, as stated by Yong et al. in 2021, had been influenced by three main factors, namely; (1) changes in societal demands for accessible health care, (2) the need for differentiating the role of community pharmacists in the sector, and (3) emergence of new applications and approaches within the scope of pharmaceutical expertise.

Those recent developments in the field created a new opportunity called “value-added” services, diverging from the traditional “checking,” “counseling,” and “dispensing” roles of a community pharmacist (Chukwu, 2020). According to Desselle et al., such developments include community-based vaccinations, safe medication disposal, chronic disease intervention and management, medication therapy adherence, therapeutic drug monitoring, and medication reconciliation.

Despite that, however, patients often perceive Pharmacists as less than that of a doctor, especially in a community pharmacy setting where they are seen as sellers of medicine. Based on the study conducted by Um et al. in 2012, patients did not expect pharmacists to have knowledge of other healthcare-related services and that the motivations of pharmacists are related to gaining profit from such services. Patients did not fully understand the concept of pharmaceutical care. In the Philippines, the observed patterns in pharmacy workforce usage raised severe challenges and concerns that must be addressed based on the results from the study conducted by Loquias & Robles in 2012. The capacity of a care system to handle drug quality problems, rational medication usage, and patient compliance is critical.

Pharmacy utilization in the Philippines, especially the ever-accessible community pharmacies, can be improved. Very little published literature in the Philippines comprehensively covers the utilization rate for Value-Added Pharmacy Services domestically. Improving the awareness and perception of the public will help develop the accessibility and quality of those value-added pharmacy services.

That said, the research aims to explore the perceptions of Filipinos for such services, specifically senior citizens living in Dasmariñas Cavite. Income level, age, and educational background may affect how senior citizens perceive those services, whether they benefit their community and overall health management.

Research Questions

Generally, the study aims to determine the patient's attitude toward paying for Value-Added Community Pharmacy Services.

Specifically, the study would answer the following questions:

What is the relationship between the Socio-demographic background of the Senior Citizens and their attitude toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services?

1. Socio-Demographic Background of the Respondents
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
 - 1.3. Income Status
 - 1.4. Educational Background
2. Awareness of the Community Pharmacy and Value-Added Services
 - 2.1. How did the Respondents know about Value-added Community Pharmacy services?
 - 2.2. Reasons for Going to the Community Pharmacy
 - 2.2.1 Health Status/Disease and Co-morbidity of the Patient
 - 2.2.2 Information and Advice
 - 2.2.3 Health and Hygiene Products
 - 2.2.4 Senior Citizen Medication Benefits
3. Attitude on Paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services
 - 3.1. Community-based Vaccinations and drug administration
 - 3.2. Smoking Cessation
 - 3.3. Obesity and Weight Management
 - 3.4. Extemporaneous Compounding
 - 3.5. Rectal Suppositories Administration
 - 3.6. Warfarin Management
 - 3.7. Medication reconciliation
 - 3.8. Management of Minor Illnesses
 - 3.9. Prescription Adjustments
4. How does the senior citizen's awareness correlate to their attitude on paying for value-added community Pharmacy services
5. How does senior citizen's awareness affect their attitude on paying for value-added community Pharmacy

METHODOLOGY

The study focused on Dasmariñas Cavite, Philippines. Dasmariñas Cavite has a population of 703,141 people, 39,787 of whom are counted as senior citizens. This populace is spread among 75 barangays (PhilAtlas, 2021).

The research participants were Senior Citizens (Over 60 years old) residing in Dasmariñas Cavite when the data-gathering procedure commenced. The participants

were grouped demographically, using Age Brackets, Gender, Income, Pension Levels, and Educational Attainment. One hundred eighty-nine senior citizens participated in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

Age Bracket	Gender	Income and Pension Levels	Educational Attainment
60 to 70 years old	Male	Non-earners and dependents	Elementary Graduate
			High School Graduate
71 to 80 years old	Female	Business Owners	Technical/Vocational
		Pensioners	College Graduate, B. S. Degree
81 years old and above			With Higher Studies (M. S. to Ph. D)

Exclusion Criteria

Any participants not within the specified inclusion criteria will be excluded.

Data Gathering Procedure

Due to the restrictions brought about by the COVID19 Pandemic and considering the safety of the researchers and the participants, the researchers used a convenience sampling method. The participants were chosen if they met the onsite or online criteria. In the case of onsite, participants were chosen directly by approaching them. For the online survey, the researchers sent the survey form through various acquaintances known to live in Dasmarinas Cavite. This ensured that the data gathered from this research represented the actual populace best.

The research utilized a survey questionnaire as a medium, and the data were collected through an online survey using google forms. The survey was sent to acquaintances using social media for direct or indirect dissemination to qualified senior citizens. The onsite survey included directly approaching senior citizens to answer the survey and disseminating those surveys at various barangays in Dasmariñas, Cavite.

The survey utilized Poka-Yoke elements to ensure the answers were as legitimate as possible. Poka-Yoke elements use mistake-proofing by providing predetermined answers, such as multiple-choice questions.

Research Instrument

The research utilized a tailored survey based on a synthesized literature review. The survey was uploaded on an online platform like google forms. The questionnaire was composed of the following:

The first part of the survey focused on the Personal Data Collection and Demographics such as Age, Gender, Income Level, and Educational Attainment of the senior citizens.

The second part of the survey established the awareness of the senior citizens of the roles and value-added services of the Community Pharmacy. The Likert Scale was composed of 4 - strongly agree, 3 - agree, 2 - disagree, and 1 - strongly disagree to avoid neutral standpoints.

The last part of the survey assessed the patient's attitude toward paying under certain specified conditions. The Likert scale was used to establish the correlation between the factors that affect the patient's attitude toward paying.

Data Analysis Procedure

The results of the demographic profile of the respondents (age, gender, income level, and educational attainment), awareness of the value-added pharmacy service (aware or not aware), and perceived attitude on paying (as to agree or disagree) were presented using frequency and percentage distribution tables and figures.

Spearman's Coefficient test was used to determine how Senior citizens' awareness correlates to their attitude on paying for value-added community Pharmacy services.

In Spearman's Coefficient Test, the value of r ranges from +1 (Positive Correlation) to -1 (Negative Correlation).

Spearman's Coefficient Test measures the strength and direction of association between two variables. It provides the best fit through the data of two variables and the value of ρ indicates how far this data points to the best fit.

Chi-square test was used to determine how Senior citizens' awareness affects their attitude toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services and how their awareness affects their attitude on paying for such services. The chi-square test is best used if observed results are in line with expected results and to rule out that observations are due to chance. A chi-square test is a suitable statistical tool when the variable in question is categorical. It is also useful when judging the goodness of fit between expected and observed results and the independence of two criteria for the classification of qualitative variables.

RESULTS

1. Socio-Demographic Background of the Respondents

The study was done on 189 participants, with 65.08% (n = 123) of the senior citizens surveyed female and 34.92% (n = 66) male. Most respondents are from the 60- to 70-year-old age range (n = 134) or recent senior citizens, and 42.86% (n = 81) are in the non-earners and dependents category. 37.04% (n = 70) of the respondents finished their college education, while respondents with only a high school diploma came second at 33.33% (n = 63).

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents		
Age Composition		
	Count	Percent
60 to 70 Years Old	134	70.90%
71 to 80 Years Old	55	29.10%
Over 80 Years Old	0	0%
Gender Composition		
Male	66	34.92%
Female	123	65.08%
Income Type		
Non-Earners and Dependents	81	42.86%
Pensioners	78	41.27%
Business Owners	30	15.87%
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Graduate	17	8.99%
High School Graduate	63	33.33%
Technical/Vocational	37	19.58%
College Graduate, BS Degree	70	37.04%
With Higher Studies (M.S. to Ph.D.)	2	1.06%

2. Awareness of the Community Pharmacy and Value-Added Service

Most of the senior citizen respondents (50.26%, n = 95) on the survey visit a pharmacy at least 2-3 times a month to buy medicine for their existing illness and for maintenance (48%). Respondents also collect some senior citizen benefits like free medications from social programs and blood pressure monitoring.

	Count	Percent
Never	1	0.53%
Once or more per week	26	13.76%
2–3 times per month	95	50.26%
Every few months	63	33.33%
Once per year	4	2.12%
Total	189	

	Count	Percent
To buy medicine for Health Status/Disease and Co-morbidity of the Patient	178	48%
Information and Advice	29	8%
Health and Hygiene Products	65	18%
Pregnancy and Newborn Care	4	1%
Senior Citizen Medication Benefits	92	25%
Total	368	

Among the 189 respondents, 138 people (73.02% of the responders) were not aware of any Value-added pharmacy services offered by community pharmacies, with only 17 responders (8.99%) saying that they were fully aware of the services and 14 responders (7.41%) says they are somewhat aware, in this case, being somewhat aware means the responders know less than 50% of the offered services while. Twenty responders (10.58%) say they are mostly aware of such services, meaning they know more than 50% of the services but less than 100%.

Figure 1. Awareness of Value-added Pharmacy Services

Among those who were aware, most obtained the information through word of mouth (17%), with 36 respondents knowing that their community pharmacy offers value-added services through their colleagues. Flyers and leaflets are the second-best methods, with 22 responders and 11 responders saying they were able to know value-added services through onsite promotion. Medication reconciliation has the highest number of respondents who were aware of the service (30 respondents), followed by Community-Based Vaccinations (27 respondents), with Management of Minor Illnesses and Prescription adjustments tied at 3rd place, both having 25 respondents who were aware of the service. The services with the least awareness are smoking cessation, with four responders aware of the service, and obesity and weight management having 0 awareness of the service. Since most responders are unaware of any community pharmacy services, they answered none of the above. Most value-added services, especially rectal suppositories (11%), are administered during medical missions and checkups.

Table 4. Awareness of Value-Added Services (Most Aware Of) (Multi-Response)		
	Count	Percent
Community-based vaccinations	27	9%
Obesity and Weight Management	0	0%
Extemporaneous Compounding	5	2%

Rectal Suppositories Administration	11	4%
Warfarin Management	24	8%
Medication Reconciliation	30	10%
Management of Minor Illnesses	25	9%
Prescription Adjustments	25	9%
Smoking Cessation	4	1%
None of the Above	137	48%
Total	288	

Table 5. Source of Information for Value-Added Pharmacy Services (Multi-Response)		
	Count	Percent
TV Commercial	6	3%
Social Media Advertisement	6	3%
Onsite Promotion and Marketing	11	5%
Flyers and Leaflets	22	10%
Word of Mouth	36	17%
I don't know	134	62%
Total	215	

Table 6 shows the attitude of senior citizens about the value-added services they deemed worth paying. Among those services, community-based vaccinations are considered the worthiest to be paid for, while obesity, weight management, and smoking cessation are deemed unworthy of any payment.

Table 6. Attitude on Value-Added Pharmacy Services (Worth Paying) (Multi-Response)		
	Count	Percent
Community-based vaccinations	56	16%
Obesity and Weight Management	7	2%
Extemporaneous Compounding	10	3%
Rectal Suppositories Administration	40	11%
Warfarin Management	24	7%
Medication Reconciliation	23	6%
Management of Minor Illnesses	48	14%
Prescription Adjustments	42	12%
Smoking Cessation	6	2%
None of the Above	98	28%
Total	354	

3. Attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services

Table 7. Attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee (Likert's Scale)		
	Count	Percent
1 (Strongly Disagree)	102	53.97%
2	45	23.81%
3	36	19.05%
4 (Strongly Agree)	6	3.17%
Total	189	

Table 8. Justification for Attitude on paying for value-added pharmacy services with Equipment and Material Cost (Likert's Scale)		
	Count	Percent
1 (Strongly Disagree)	85	44.97%
2	43	22.75%
3	53	28.04%
4 (Strongly Agree)	8	4.23%

Table 9. Justification for Attitude on Paying for value-added pharmacy Services with Subsidy (Likert's Scale)		
	Count	Percent
1 (Strongly Disagree)	42	22.22%
2	5	2.65%
3	33	17.46%
4 (Strongly Agree)	109	57.67%
Total	189	

3.1. Relationship between the Socio-demographic background of the Senior Citizens and their attitude toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services

Table 10. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's age and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	7.407717	0.059978	7.814728	no

Based on Table 10, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' age and their Attitude toward paying a Minimum Fee.

Table 11. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's age and their willingness to pay for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Equipment and Material Cost				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	3.802702	0.283572	7.814728	no

Based on Table 11, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' age and their attitude toward paying for Equipment and Material Costs.

Table 12. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's age and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Subsidy				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	6.800895	0.078522	7.814728	no

Based on Table 12, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can conclude that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' age and their attitude toward paying with Subsidy.

Table 13. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's gender and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	6.54341	0.087966	7.814728	no

Based on Table 13, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can conclude that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' gender and their Attitude toward paying a Minimum Fee.

Table 14. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's gender and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Equipment and Material Cost				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	5.583779	0.133713	7.814728	no

Based on Table 14, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can conclude that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' gender and their attitude toward paying Equipment and Material Costs.

Table 15. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's awareness and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Subsidy				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	10.40577	0.015414	7.814728	yes

Based on Table 15, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between senior citizen's gender and their attitude on paying if the Value-Added pharmacy services are subsidized, with the majority of female respondents (59.40% strongly agreeing and 12.20% Agreeing) willing to pay for Value-Added pharmacy services with subsidy compared to their male counterparts (54.55% strongly agreeing and 27.27% agreeing).

Table 16. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's income level and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	33.80049	0.00000735	12.59159	yes

Based on Table 16, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, a significant relationship exists between patients' income level and their attitude toward paying Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee. Based on cross-tabulation, most non-earners and dependents respondents are unwilling to pay for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with a Minimum Fee.

Table 17. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's income level and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Equipment and Material Cost				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	26.43699	0.000185	12.59159	yes

Based on Table 17, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, a significant relationship exists between patients' income level and their Attitude toward paying for Equipment and Material Costs. Based on the data, most non-earners and dependents responders are unwilling to pay for Value-Added pharmacy services with Equipment and Material Costs.

Table 18. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's income level and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Subsidy				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	11.29917	0.079559	12.59159	no

Based on Table 18, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' income level and their attitude toward paying with Subsidy.

Table 19. Crosstabulation between senior citizen's educational attainment and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	64.63454	0.00000000318	21.02607	yes

Based on Table 19, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, a significant relationship exists between a patient's educational attainment and their attitude toward paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee. Most respondents with a High School diploma are unwilling to pay for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee. In contrast, most of the Responders with College Level Degrees agree to pay.

Table 20. Crosstabulation between senior citizen's educational attainment and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Equipment and Material Cost				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	50.86066	9.86E-07	21.02607	yes

Based on Table 20, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between a patient's educational attainment and their attitude toward paying for equipment and material costs. Based on cross-tabulation, most high school graduate responders would prefer to pay for Value-Added pharmacy services with equipment and material costs. In contrast, the majority of the college graduate respondents agree to pay.

Table 21. Crosstabulation between senior citizen's educational attainment and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Subsidy				
Chi-Square Test				
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	48.75076	2.31E-06	21.02607	yes

Based on Table 21, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore a significant relationship exists between a patient's educational attainment and their attitude toward paying with a subsidy, with most of the respondents with a college degree willing to pay with a subsidy. Though not the majority, many respondents with high school education are not willing to pay for Value-added pharmacy services even with a subsidy.

4. How does Senior citizens' awareness correlate to their attitude on paying for value-added community Pharmacy services?

Table 22. Spearman's coefficient Test for Selected Correlations						
	α	Tails	ρ	t-stat	p-value	
Correlation between patient's awareness and their Attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee	0.05	2	0.708937	13.74584	0.00000001	
Correlation between patient awareness and their Attitude to paying	0.05	2	0.57060184	9.50147073	0.000000001	

for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Equipment and Material Cost					
Correlation between patient awareness and their Attitude to paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Subsidy	0.05	2	0.090556	1.243438	0.215263

Based on Table 22, the p-value for the correlation between patients' awareness and their Attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee using Spearman's coefficient test is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a correlation between patients' awareness and their Attitude toward paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee. The rho for this correlation value is 0.708937, indicating a strong positive correlation.

Meanwhile, the p-value for the correlation between patients' awareness and their Attitude to paying Equipment and Material Cost is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can conclude that there is a correlation between patients' awareness and their Attitude to paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee, with a rho value of = 0.57060184. This indicates that there is a strong positive correlation.

Lastly, based on the table, the p-value is more significant than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a correlation between patients' awareness and their Attitude toward paying with Subsidy.

5. How Senior citizens' awareness affects their attitude on paying for value-added community Pharmacy services

Table 23. Cross tabulation table between patient's awareness and their attitude on paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee				
Chi-Square Test				
SUMMARY		Alpha	0.05	
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	127.3925	0.0000001	16.91898	yes

Based on Table 23, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' awareness and their Attitude toward paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee. Based on the results of the chi-square test and cross-tabulation, awareness about the program is one of the factors for the patient's willingness to pay for Value-Added Pharmacy Services for a Minimum Fee.

Table 24. Cross tabulation table between senior citizen's awareness and their attitude on paying for value-added pharmacy services with Equipment and Material Cost				
Chi-Square Test				
SUMMARY	Alpha		0.05	
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	108.2683	0.0000001	16.91898	yes

Based on Table 24, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it can conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' awareness and their Attitude toward paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services with Equipment and Material Costs. Based on the results of the chi-square test and cross-tabulation, awareness about the program is one of the factors for the patient to be willing to pay for the services with Equipment and Material Costs.

Table 25. Cross Tabulation between senior citizen's awareness and their attitude on paying for value-added pharmacy services with Subsidy				
Chi-Square Test				
SUMMARY	Alpha		0.05	
	<i>chi-sq</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>x-crit</i>	<i>sig</i>
Max likelihood	34.75036	0.00007	16.91898	yes

Based on Table 25, the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore it can conclude that there is a significant relationship between patients' awareness and their Attitude toward paying with subsidy. Based on the results of the chi-square test and cross-tabulation, awareness about the program is one of the factors for the patient's willingness to pay for the services with a subsidy.

DISCUSSION

According to the study done by Desselle et al. in 2019, value-added community pharmacy services are needed by vulnerable populations, especially older patients with diminished access to healthcare. Since only 17 respondents (8.99%) said, they were fully aware of the services, and 14 respondents (7.41%) said they were somewhat aware. Less than 50% of the respondents knew the offered services. Of the 189 respondents, 138 people (73.02%) needed to be made aware of any Value-added pharmacy services provided by community pharmacies. Making sure that these

services are known is more likely to impact the overall patient care experience positively.

Among the value-added services listed in the statement of the problem, medication reconciliation is the top pick. In simpler terms, it is creating the most accurate medication list to increase patient safety, decrease medication-related issues, and improve health outcomes, according to Goode et al. in 2019. It focuses on medication optimization, and community pharmacists are emerging in the transitions of care area to help decrease readmissions rates and emergency room visits and increase healthcare cost savings

Tanael et al. tackled the issue of the view of Filipino pharmacists on community pharmacy-based vaccination programs in 2016, with the majority of them favorably supporting the program. Community-based immunizations are among those considered the most deserving of money. This low-lying fruit can be the pioneer in advertising the services to senior citizens, with some needing a “cost-effective” jab of the latest vaccine. Filipino pharmacists are aware of their competence level and highly accept offering community-based vaccination.

The respondents' attitudes toward paying if a service has a minimal fee are primarily influenced by the senior citizens' income level ($p = 0.00000735$) and educational level ($p = 0.0000000318$). Most senior citizens with a college degree agree to pay, unlike those with only a high school diploma, who do not. Respondents who depend on their families are also more inclined to object to paying a minimal charge for a value-added pharmacy service.

Regarding the respondents' attitude on paying for a service that has a justifiable material and equipment cost, it is mainly affected by the income level ($p = 0.000185$) and educational attainment ($p = 0.000000986$) of the senior citizens. Most of those who were non-earners and dependent and with a high school level education is not willing to pay for Value-Added pharmaceutical services even if there is a good material and equipment cost associated with such service.

Male respondents are more likely to agree to pay for services if there is a subsidy; 59.40% of the male respondents indicated they would be willing to pay. The respondent's level of education can also influence their opinion toward paying with a subsidy, with most respondents with a college degree being open to doing so. However, even with a subsidy, a sizable portion of respondents with a high school diploma are unwilling to pay for value-added pharmaceutical services while not being the majority.

Regarding the correlation between senior citizens' awareness and their attitude toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services for a minimum fee, there is a strong positive correlation between patient awareness and that attitude with a rho value of 0.708937. Since there is a high positive correlation between the patient's awareness and their attitude about paying, indicating that there is a direct relationship between the two. As the level of awareness increases, the attitude toward paying also increases.

A strong positive correlation is also observed between patients' awareness and their Attitude toward paying Equipment and Material Costs. A direct relationship exists

between a patient's awareness and attitude toward paying. As the level of awareness increases, the attitude toward paying also increases. However, no significant correlation was observed between patients' awareness and their Attitude to paying with Subsidy.

Lastly, considering the respondents' awareness and their relationship with the attitude on paying, there was an established relationship between the senior citizen's awareness and their attitude toward paying for Value-Added Pharmacy Services, with awareness about the services being one of the contributing factors to their willingness to pay for such services. If senior citizens are more aware, they are more inclined to pay, even if the program has a minimum fee or a subsidy.

Conclusions

The study's findings revealed a significant positive correlation between awareness of value-added community pharmacy services and attitude towards paying among senior citizens. As the level of awareness increased, the attitude towards paying for these services also improved. Participants who were more aware of the services were more likely to express a positive attitude towards paying for them through out-of-pocket payments or insurance coverage.

These findings highlight the importance of increasing awareness among senior citizens about the value-added services offered by community pharmacies and how they can positively impact their attitude toward paying for these services. The results suggest that efforts to educate and inform senior citizens about the benefits of these services may lead to greater acceptance and utilization of these services, which can ultimately improve health outcomes and enhance the role of community pharmacies in supporting the healthcare needs of older adults.

The study revealed that income level and educational attainment were significant factors associated with senior citizens' attitudes toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services. Participants with higher income levels and higher educational attainment were more likely to express a positive attitude toward paying for these services.

On the other hand, age and gender were found to have a weak or negligible relationship with the attitude toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services among senior citizens. These factors were not found to be significant predictors of attitude towards paying.

These results highlight the importance of income level and educational attainment as key socio-demographic factors influencing senior citizens' attitudes toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services. Understanding these factors can inform pharmacy practice and policy-making in tailoring interventions and strategies to promote the utilization of these services among older adults. Furthermore, the findings suggest that age and gender may not be significant factors in predicting the attitude toward paying for these services among senior citizens. Other socio-demographic characteristics may play a more prominent role.

Recommendations

Further research is warranted to explore additional socio-demographic factors that may impact senior citizens' attitudes toward paying for value-added community pharmacy services and better understand the underlying mechanisms driving these relationships. This research has implications for designing targeted interventions to promote access and utilization of value-added community pharmacy services among diverse populations of older adults.

The research demonstrated that most responding senior citizens in Dasmarinas Cavite must be aware of value-added pharmacy services offered in their community. However, gathering data and insights from other demographics, such as age, nationality, and religion, will further improve the study. This study is suggested to be used as a model for designing related research.

Further research on the Pharmacists' perspective is also warranted. Since the study did not include the community pharmacy itself, achieving a holistic approach to the problem is recommended. Future researchers must also conduct community pharmacy profiling and determine which services are feasible for a local community pharmacy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers, began disseminating the survey form as soon as approval to conduct the study was available. The participants in this study gave their full consent to participate, and they were allowed to withdraw or have their responses redacted at any time. There were no risks to the participating respondents during the course of the study's implementation.

Any confidentiality violations that occurred while the research was being conducted were the researchers' responsibility. Only the researchers, the adviser, and the statistician had access to the data obtained to maintain the confidentiality of the information gathered. All data from the study that was stored on the drive was to be treated as confidential and only utilized for research.

To the extent permitted by the Data Privacy Act of 2012, each research subject's identity was maintained as anonymously as possible. Only the first Letter of the participant's first name and surname were recorded. After the hard-bound form of the research output was submitted and published in the library, all encrypted and unencrypted data were to be erased.

No conflict of interest was found in this study. The study had passed the plagiarism check using Turnitin software and had a grade of 8%. The data were interpreted objectively based on statistical analysis, and the results were used solely for research purposes.

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